

Relation of the Poisson Distribution to the Binomial Theorem

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In (1), it is shown that the Poisson distribution is an $n \rightarrow$ infinite limit of the binomial expression $\binom{n}{k} (b/n)^k (1-b/n)^{n-k}$. Here b is the average number of successes for a time interval. We argue that $2b$ should then be the average number of successes in twice the time interval. Then, for twice the interval, one has the distribution $(2b)^n / n! \exp(-2b)$. This should be equivalent to the sum of all single interval scenarios which yield n successes for the Poisson distribution. We show that this is the case using the binomial theorem and generalized to the $(a+b)$ power n case.

Poisson Distribution

The Poisson distribution is given by: $P(n) = b^n / n! \exp(-b)$ ((1))

n is the number of successes and b , the average number of successes in a time interval. One may note that for n_1, n_2 , the product:

$$b^{n_1} * b^{n_2} = b^{(n_1+n_2)} \quad ((2))$$

This suggests considering product scenarios of Poisson distributions.

Product Poisson Distributions

We consider the case of doubling the interval linked to a Poisson distribution characterized by b . Then:

$$2b \text{ successes on average in the double interval and } P_2(n) = (2b)^n / n! \exp(-2b) \quad ((3))$$

A double interval, however, is made of two single intervals and one should be able to consider AND probabilities in each. Then:

$$\exp(-b)\exp(-b) \rightarrow \exp(-2b) \text{ and } b^i b^{(n-i)} = (1/2)^n (2b)^n \text{ so:}$$

$$(1/2)^n \sum_{i=0, n} 1/i! 1/(n-i)! \text{ should equal } 1/n! \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{Using the binomial theorem: } (1+1)^n = \sum_{i=0, n} \binom{n}{i} = 2^n$$

one immediately obtains ((4)).

More General Case

In the more general case, one may consider:

$$(a+b)^n / n! = \sum_{i=0}^n \frac{a^i b^{n-i}}{i! (n-i)!} \quad ((5))$$

The product combination of a a and b average successes is:

$$\sum_{i=0}^n \frac{a^i b^{n-i}}{i! (n-i)!} \quad ((6))$$

$$((6)) \text{ is equivalent to: } \frac{1}{n!} (a+b)^n \quad ((7))$$

Thus, the Poisson distribution is very closely linked with the binomial theorem.

Using the Binomial Theorem to Guess the n! Factor

Imagine that one has a very small average value per time interval b and argues for a power law, i.e.

$$B^n \text{ where } n \text{ is the number of successes} \quad ((8))$$

One might consider enhancing this by a function of n, i.e. f(n). In addition, there would be a normalization factor C(b). One must consider the idea of a product of probabilities. If one simply doubles the time interval, then:

$$C(2b) f(n) (2b)^n = \sum_{i=0}^n C(b)C(b) f(i) f(n-i) b^n \quad ((9))$$

If f(n) is a function of n, but not of b, then C(2b)=C(b)C(b) means that C(b) = exp(C1 b) is a solution. Furthermore, then:

$$\sum_{i=0}^n f(i) b^i = \exp(C1b) \text{ which immediately leads to } f(i) = 1/i! \text{ Which also satisfies } ((9)). \text{ This argument may be generalized to the } (a+b)^n \text{ case as well.}$$

One might argue that f(b,i), but it seems that the dependence on b has already been postulated in ((8)).

Thus, product probabilities seem to tell quite a bit about distributions in some cases as in the Poisson, but also in the Maxwell-Boltzmann situation. There, one has $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ forcing $p(e_i)=C \exp(-e_i/T)$. In the Poisson case, starting with an unknown f(i), but considering AND product probabilities leads to the Poisson form, assuming ((8)). Without the product form, one would possibly stop at ((8)) which is incomplete.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the Poisson distribution is closely linked to the binomial theorem if one considers products of Poisson probabilities for various scenarios. We suggest that

considering product probabilities can sometimes reveal the properties of a distribution as in the Poisson case (if one assumes ((8))) and also in the Maxwell-Boltzmann situation.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Poisson_distribution